

A Hierarchical Dynamical Model of Learning, Forgetting, and Relearning

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Abstract

The model developed here provides a quantitative account of a range of well-known findings on learning, forgetting, and relearning, spanning delays from seconds (e.g., Peterson & Peterson, 1959) to weeks (e.g., Ebbinghaus, 1885/1964; Perkins, 1914). The model tracks the probability of recall of individual items as they are learned, forgotten, and relearned over time. During study, recall probability increases, whereas during retention intervals it declines exponentially. Crucially, the rate of this decline is not fixed but is governed by a forgetting exponent that itself changes across study and delay periods. These changes are organised within a hierarchy of interacting processes operating over multiple timescales, allowing recall dynamics to evolve systematically across study and delay. This structure allows the model to capture effects of serial position, list length, spacing, and long-term retention within a single framework. Although classic studies such as those of Ebbinghaus, Peterson and Peterson, and Perkins are often treated as demonstrations of separate phenomena, the present model shows that they can be understood as arising from a common set of underlying processes.

1. Introduction

The principles governing the learning, retention, and recall of verbal material have been a central concern of experimental psychology since the work of Hermann Ebbinghaus (1885/1964). This work has established a number of robust empirical phenomena, including the characteristic form of the forgetting curve, serial position effects, and effects of massed versus distributed learning. However, these findings are typically treated as separate effects, and there is no widely accepted quantitative framework that integrates them within a single model.

The model described here provides such a framework. It accounts for the results of several well-known experiments involving both individual items (e.g., nonsense syllables) and lists of such items, across retention intervals ranging from seconds to weeks. Central to the model is the tracking of the probability of recall of individual items as they are learned, forgotten, and relearned over successive study and delay periods.

The model is formulated as a hierarchical dynamical system in which the rate of forgetting evolves as a function of study and delay. It relies exclusively on objective, measurable variables that influence recall, including study duration, retention interval, and list structure (e.g., serial position and list length). A central feature of the model is that forgetting is governed by an exponent that itself changes over time, giving rise to interacting processes operating at multiple timescales.

In outline, recall probability increases during study and declines exponentially during retention intervals, with the rate of decline determined by parameters that depend on prior study and list structure. These parameters are themselves subject to systematic change across study and delay periods, allowing the model to capture a range of empirical phenomena within a unified framework. A detailed specification of the model is provided in the following section.

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2. Model overview

The model employs only objective, measurable factors that can influence recall. These include:

- the probability with which an item could be guessed before being encountered;
- the duration for which the item is available for study;
- the duration of the delay between study and a subsequent attempt at recall or relearning;
- the number of items that precede the item in a list;
- the number of items that follow it;
- the total length of the list;
- the pattern and duration of study periods and delays prior to recall.

The model is formulated as a hierarchical dynamical system in which the rate of forgetting evolves over time as a function of study and delay. In outline, it incorporates the following features:

1. The initial probability of recall of an item (e.g., a nonsense syllable) prior to presentation corresponds to its likelihood of being produced by chance. Following even a brief period of study, this probability typically rises to a value close to 1.00.
2. After the completion of study, there is a short interval (approximately 2 seconds) during which little or no measurable forgetting occurs. Thereafter, recall probability declines exponentially during any delay preceding a recall attempt, governed by an operative forgetting exponent.
3. The rate of forgetting (i.e., the operative forgetting exponent) depends on the duration of study and on two underlying parameters described below.
4. In lists of items, the initial value of the forgetting exponent (prior to study) depends on serial position. Early and late items have lower initial values than items near the middle, forming an inverted-U pattern.
5. The extent to which the forgetting exponent is reduced during study depends on a reducing exponent, which also varies with serial position (in a U-shaped pattern), as well as on the duration of study. Together, these determine the operative forgetting exponent.
6. During delays, both the forgetting exponent and the reducing exponent tend to return toward their initial values. These changes do not affect the course of forgetting within the current delay, but determine the parameter values that apply in subsequent study and delay periods. As a result, the operative forgetting exponent governing each delay depends on the evolving underlying state established through prior study and delay periods.
7. The reducing exponent is itself subject to further modulation. It increases during study periods and may decrease during delays. The magnitude of this decrease becomes important when learning is distributed over extended periods. It depends on delay measured in 'relative time', defined as the ratio between:
(a) the time from the beginning of the first study period to the end of the delay preceding recall, and
(b) the time from the beginning of the first study period to the end of the most recent study period.

3. Empirical Foundations of the Model

The model developed here is grounded in a set of experimental findings that collectively constrain the form that any general account of memory must take. These studies were selected because they provide sufficiently detailed procedural descriptions and quantitative data, and because, taken together, they span a wide range of timescales and learning conditions.

Specifically, they address: (i) the short-term retention of individual items over delays of a few seconds; (ii) the acquisition of lists over repeated trials and the emergence of serial position effects;

(iii) long-term retention and relearning over intervals of days or weeks; and (iv) the effects of distributed as opposed to massed practice.

The experiments of Hellyer (1962) and Robinson and Brown (1926) are central to the first two domains, while the work of Ebbinghaus (1885/1964) and Perkins (1914) extends the analysis to longer timescales and more complex patterns of learning. Taken together, these findings provide a coherent empirical basis for the development of a unified quantitative model of learning and forgetting.

3.1 Short-term retention: Hellyer (1962)

Hellyer (1962) investigated the recall of consonant trigrams following delays ranging from 3 to 27 seconds. The stimuli were presented visually, allowing precise control over the duration of exposure. Each trigram was presented for 1 second either once or repeated consecutively 2, 4, or 8 times, with participants required to read it aloud on each presentation.

During the retention interval, participants engaged in a distractor task, reading aloud numbers presented to them, thereby preventing rehearsal.

The results are shown in Figure 1. They demonstrate that increasing the duration of study produces a systematic reduction in the rate of forgetting. This finding places a strong constraint on any quantitative model, requiring that the rate of decay depends directly on prior study.

Figure 1. Recall probability as a function of delay in Hellyer (1962), for different durations of initial presentation (1, 2, 4, and 8 seconds). Longer study durations are associated with a slower rate of forgetting, constraining how the rate of decay must depend on prior study.

3.2 List learning dynamics: Robinson & Brown (1926)

Robinson and Brown (1926) investigated the learning of lists of nonsense syllables using an anticipation procedure. Lists contained 6, 9, 12, 15, or 18 items; however, because the first item served as a prompt, the number of items to be learned was effectively 5, 8, 11, 14, or 17. Their results were presented in a series of figures (Figures I–XIV, pp. 545–550), from which the probability of recall for individual items across trials can be extracted.

Each list was first presented once in a continuous sequence on a memory drum, with each item shown for 2 seconds. Immediately thereafter, the anticipation phase began: the first item (the prompt) was presented again, and participants attempted to produce the second item; the second item was then presented, prompting recall of the third, and so on. This cycle continued without interruption until all items were recalled correctly.

The results show that individual items are acquired at different rates across repetitions, and that recall varies systematically with serial position. Early and late items tend to be learned more rapidly than those in the middle of the list, producing a characteristic serial position curve that evolves

over trials. Because correct recall of the entire list depends on the slowest item, these data place strong constraints on any model of learning.

Specifically, a successful model must account simultaneously for (i) item-specific learning trajectories across trials and (ii) systematic variation in recall as a function of serial position. These constraints are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Data from Robinson and Brown (1926) illustrating key constraints on list learning. Left-hand panel: individual items within a list are learned at different rates across successive repetitions. Right-hand panel: the serial position curve, showing superior recall for early and late items and poorer recall for items in the middle, with this pattern evolving across trials. These findings require any model of learning to account for both item-specific dynamics and systematic serial position effects.

3.3 Long-term retention: Ebbinghaus (1885/1964)

Ebbinghaus (1885/1964) conducted a series of experiments on his own learning using lists of nonsense syllables of varying length. He prepared many such lists, each composed of randomly selected syllables, and learned them using a procedure broadly similar to that employed by Robinson and Brown.

Each list was read through repeatedly at a steady rate (approximately five syllables every 2 seconds, often paced by a metronome) until it could be reproduced correctly from memory. Learning was considered complete when the entire list could be recited without error, typically on one or, in some cases, two successive attempts. To assess retention, Ebbinghaus relearned the lists after delays of varying duration and measured the saving in time or repetitions required relative to the initial learning.

Two of his most important findings are illustrated in Figure 3. First, the number of repetitions required to learn a list increases systematically with its length, placing constraints on how the accumulation of learning must scale with the amount of material. Second, the amount retained, as measured by savings during relearning, declines with increasing delay, producing a characteristic forgetting function with a rapid initial decline followed by a slower rate of loss over longer intervals.

Together, these findings place essential constraints on any model of memory. A successful account must capture both the scaling of learning with list length and the retention of material over extended timescales, including the relationship between initial learning and subsequent relearning.

Figure 3. Data from Ebbinghaus (1885/1964) illustrating constraints on learning and long-term retention. Left-hand panel: the number of repetitions required to learn a list increases with list length, constraining how the accumulation of learning must scale with the amount of material. Right-hand panel: the percentage of time saved during relearning decreases as the delay increases, showing a characteristic forgetting function with a rapid initial decline followed by a slower rate of forgetting over longer intervals. Together, these findings require a model that can account for both the scaling of learning and the retention of material over extended timescales.

3.4 *Massed versus distributed learning: Perkins (1914)*

Perkins (1914) conducted one of the earliest systematic investigations of massed versus distributed learning. In her experiment, a list of 14 nonsense syllables was studied in blocks of 1, 2, 4, or 8 repetitions, with these blocks spaced at intervals of 1, 2, 3, or 4 days, until a total of 16 repetitions had been completed. As a result, learning could occur over periods ranging from as little as two days (8 repetitions per session with a 1-day interval) to as many as 61 days (1 repetition per session with 4-day intervals). Recall was tested 14 days after the final study session.

Only four participants took part in Perkins' study, and not all served in all 16 conditions. Perkins presented the average recall in each condition of all the participants who had provided data for that condition. She did not herself calculate the average recall for the blocks of different sizes (i.e., the number of readings per day) or for the intervals of different lengths, but Woodworth (1947, p. 213) subsequently tabulated the means and Baddeley (1976) presented a figure displaying these mean values, which is reproduced here as Figure 4.

Perkins' method complements that of Ebbinghaus in that it provides a direct measure of recall following a delay, rather than an indirect estimate based on savings during relearning.

The results, shown in Figure 4, indicate that recall decreases as the size of study blocks increases, demonstrating that massed practice is less effective than distributing learning across multiple sessions. In contrast, variation in the interval between study sessions produces a less systematic effect within the range examined.

These findings place important constraints on any model of memory. In particular, the model must account for the influence of the temporal distribution of study on both learning and long-term retention, and for the differential effects of block size and spacing across extended timescales.

Figure 4. Data from Perkins (1914), as presented by Baddeley (1976), illustrating the effects of distributed learning. Recall decreases as the size of study blocks increases, indicating that massed practice is less effective than distributed learning. In contrast, the effect of the interval between study sessions is less systematic. These findings constrain the model to account for the influence of the temporal distribution of study on learning and retention over extended periods.

4. Development of the model

This section introduces the principal components of the model and the way in which they interact over time. The central feature is that the probability of recall of an individual item changes continuously as a function of study and delay. During study, recall probability increases, typically approaching a value close to 1.00 after even brief exposure. During subsequent delays, recall probability declines over time, and the form and rate of this decline are key features of the model.

The rate at which recall declines during a delay is governed by a parameter referred to as the *forgetting exponent*. This parameter determines how rapidly recall probability decreases as a function of time. Its value is not fixed: it depends on prior study and varies across successive episodes of learning and forgetting. The operative forgetting exponent refers to the value governing recall during a particular delay period, typically determined at the end of the preceding study period.

The forgetting exponent is modified by study. During study periods, its value is reduced, resulting in slower subsequent forgetting. The extent of this reduction is governed by a second parameter, the *reducing exponent*. During delay periods, parameters influencing the forgetting exponent continue to evolve, tending toward their initial values. These changes do not affect the course of forgetting within the current delay, but instead determine the values that will apply following subsequent study periods. The factors governing changes in the reducing exponent are described in later sections.

The general form of this process — where repeated learning progressively reduces the rate of subsequent forgetting — was anticipated in qualitative form by Woodworth (1947), who proposed that successive cycles of learning and forgetting could be represented as a series of curves of decreasing steepness. An example of this is shown in Figure 5. The present model extends this idea by providing a quantitative formulation of the processes that give rise to this pattern and by specifying how the relevant parameters evolve across study and delay.

Figure 5. Schematic representation, adapted from Woodworth (1947 Figure 15, p. 59), illustrating the progressive reduction in forgetting rate across repeated learning cycles. Each cycle of relearning increases the level of retention and reduces the rate of subsequent forgetting. The present model provides a quantitative account of this pattern.

The way in which recall probability changes for a single item is illustrated schematically in Figure 6. Prior to initial exposure, recall probability is effectively at chance level. Following brief presentation, it rises to a value close to 1.00. After a short interval of approximately two seconds during which little or no measurable forgetting occurs, recall probability declines over time. With repeated study, recall probability again approaches near-perfect levels, and subsequent forgetting proceeds more slowly, reflecting a reduction in the operative forgetting exponent. For illustration, it is shown that recall probability would eventually return toward its initial level if the delay were sufficiently prolonged.

Figure 6. Schematic illustration of the change in recall probability for an individual item across successive episodes of study and delay. Recall probability rises during study (shaded) to near 1.00 and, after a brief interval, declines over time. With repeated study, the rate of decline becomes progressively slower, although recall probability returns toward its initial level over sufficiently long delays.

4.1 Reduction of forgetting rate

Analysis of recall at longer delays in Hellyer's (1962) data shows that the fitted functions originate from a recall probability close to 1.00 approximately two seconds after presentation, after which recall declines exponentially. The rate of this decline depends on the duration of study: longer study leads to slower forgetting.

More specifically, recall probability decreases as an exponential function of the square root of study time, relative to an inferred initial value at the onset of study. This relationship provides a quantitative basis for determining how study modifies the forgetting exponent.

4.2 *Serial position effect*

In list-learning situations such as those studied by Robinson and Brown (1926), it is possible to estimate the forgetting exponent operating during the first delay period—that is, the operative forgetting exponent following initial study—for each item in a list. This exponent varies systematically with serial position.

Using the principles derived from Hellyer’s data as a starting point, it is possible to assign each item a unique initial value of the forgetting exponent and a corresponding reducing exponent governing its change during study. These initial forgetting exponent values follow an inverted U-shaped pattern across serial positions, with items in the middle of the list showing higher values than those at the beginning or end. In contrast, the reducing exponents follow a U-shaped pattern.

The combined effect is that the operative forgetting exponents of items in the middle of the list are reduced more during study than those at either end, partially offsetting the initial serial position effect (see Figure 7). The better recall of items at the beginning and end of a list is commonly referred to as primacy and recency, although in the procedures used by Robinson and Brown and by Ebbinghaus, all items are tested after comparable delays; it is therefore more accurate to refer to primacy and ultimacy effects.

The variation of the forgetting exponent across study and delay is central to understanding how lists are learned. Both the forgetting exponent and the parameters governing its change evolve over time. The forgetting exponent decreases during study, while during delay the parameters that determine it tend toward their initial values. These changes do not affect the current delay, but determine the values that will apply in subsequent study periods.

The parameters governing these changes are themselves subject to modification: the reducing exponent increases during study and may decrease during delay, while the parameter responsible for restoring the forgetting exponent may decrease during study and increase during delay. This gives rise to a hierarchy of interacting processes, in which the evolution of each component depends on the state of others. At the start of each study period, parameter values correspond to those established at the end of the preceding delay.

Figure 7. Serial position variation in the forgetting exponent and its modification during study. Left-hand panel: the initial forgetting exponent (upper points) and operative forgetting exponent (lower points) for each item in a 17-item list, showing an inverted U-shaped pattern across serial positions. Right-hand panel: the reducing exponent determining the extent to which the forgetting exponent is lowered during study, showing a complementary U-shaped pattern. Together, these patterns account for observed serial position effects.

5. The quantitative model

The central component of the model is the forgetting exponent and its evolution across successive study and delay periods. The remaining components of the model — including the acquisition function governing initial increases in recall probability and the postponement function affecting very short delays — are subsidiary mechanisms introduced to account for specific empirical features of the data.

5.1 Increase of recall probability during study

The probability of recall of an item such as a nonsense syllable made available for even a few tenths of a second is assumed to increase during study as a function of time, approaching an upper limit of 1.00. This increase is modelled as an exponential function of time, beginning at the initial probability p_0 and reaching a value p_1 at the end of the first study period (S_1). This formulation is adopted as a modelling assumption. The precise form of the acquisition function is not central to the theory developed here. Its primary role is to provide a plausible approximation to the rapid increase in recall observed during brief periods of study. Although the precise form of the increase is not established definitively, an exponential rise is consistent with empirical observations of acquisition, and is sufficient to capture the rapid improvement in recall observed following brief periods of study.

The rate of increase is governed by an exponent k . In the case of Robinson and Brown's data, the precise value of k is not critical provided that it allows recall to approach near-perfect levels after a short study period. However, for other datasets — particularly those of Ebbinghaus, where presentation times are relatively brief and list lengths are large — the value of k plays a more significant role. In these cases, it was found that k decreases systematically as a function of item position, reflecting slower acquisition for later items in longer lists.

The value of k that provided the best fit to the data overall was determined empirically and is given by:

$$k = 360I^{-2}$$

I is the serial position of the item (excluding any prompt).

The probability of recall (p_1) at the end of the first study period (S_1) is calculated as follows:

$$p_1 = 1 - [(1 - p_0)e^{-kS_1}]$$

p_0 is the initial probability of the item before any study or forgetting has occurred;

p_1 is the probability of recall at the completion of the first study period;

S_1 is the duration of the first study period (sec.).

5.2 Postponement of forgetting

Forgetting is assumed to occur exponentially following a study period. However, several of the datasets considered earlier indicate that this decline does not begin immediately. Instead, there is a short initial interval — of the order of a few seconds — during which little or no measurable forgetting occurs.

Evidence for this can be seen in Hellyer’s (1962) data, where fitted exponential functions originate from a recall probability close to 1.00 approximately two seconds after presentation. A similar effect is observable in Ebbinghaus’ (1885/1964) finding that short lists can be recalled perfectly immediately after a single presentation. This initial period of minimal forgetting is also consistent with the short-lived retention typically attributed to working memory (e.g., the phonological buffer; Baddeley, Lewis & Vallar, 1984).

To capture this feature, the model incorporates a postponement function, denoted α , which modulates the operative forgetting exponent. Immediately following study, α takes a value close to 0, and it increases smoothly toward 1 over a period of a few seconds. As a result, the effective rate of forgetting is initially reduced and gradually approaches its full value. This component is introduced primarily to account for empirical findings at very short delays and should be regarded as a local modification to the core forgetting function rather than as a separate mechanism of memory.

This mechanism has a noticeable effect when delays are short, as in the studies of Hellyer and Peterson and Peterson, but has negligible influence at longer delays. In particular, it does not affect the results of Robinson and Brown (1926), as α reaches a value close to 1 well before recall is required.

The form of the function used for α is given below, although other smooth transition functions would serve a similar purpose.

$$\alpha = (1 + e^{-b(D - D_\tau)})^{-1}$$

b : rate parameter

D : delay before recall

D_τ : value of D for which $\alpha = 0.5$

The optimal values of b and D_τ were found to be 2.25 and 3.2, respectively, for the data of Hellyer (1962) and Peterson and Peterson (1959). For Ebbinghaus’ data, slightly different values (3 and 4.52) provided a better fit, corresponding to a slower transition to the full forgetting rate. The way this factor changes as the delay increases can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Postponement function α , showing the gradual transition from negligible to full forgetting over the first few seconds following a study period. The function modulates the operative forgetting exponent, reducing the rate of forgetting at very short delays.

5.3 Recall following a single or first presentation of an item

As illustrated in Figure 8 (right-hand panel), during the first delay period (D_1) the probability of recall of an item declines exponentially as a function of time, falling from p_1 to p_2 , where p_2 is the probability of recall at the time of the first recall attempt.

The rate of this decline is governed by the forgetting exponent, denoted y . At the start of the first study period (S_1), this exponent has an initial value y_0 . During study, its value is reduced, reaching y_1 (the operative forgetting exponent) by the end of the study period (Figure 8, left-hand panel).

The reduction in the forgetting exponent during study is determined by a second parameter, q , referred to as the reducing exponent. At the start of the first study period, this parameter has a value q_0 . The value of y_1 is calculated as follows:

$$y_1 = y_0 e^{(-q_0 S_1^{0.5})}$$

where S_1 is the duration of the first study period. The values of y_0 and q_0 are defined in the following section.

During the first delay period, the value y_1 remains constant and governs the decline in recall probability. This exponent is modulated by the postponement function α , which reduces the effective rate of forgetting at short delays. Together, these determine the decline of p from p_1 to p_2 (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Calculation of the forgetting exponent and its effect on recall. Left-hand panel: reduction of the forgetting exponent from its initial value y_0 to the operative value y_1 during the first study period (S_1). Right-hand panel: resulting change in recall probability, showing the increase during study and the subsequent exponential decline during the delay period (D_1), modulated by the postponement function α .

5.4 Calculation of y_0 and q_0 (initial forgetting and reducing exponents)

The initial values of the forgetting exponent (y_0) and the reducing exponent (q_0) were determined from the data of Robinson and Brown (1926).

Assuming that the probability of recall immediately after study (p_1) is effectively 1.00, and using the observed values of recall (p_2) following the first delay period (D_1), the operative forgetting exponent (y_1) for each item can be estimated from the data of Robinson and Brown. From these values, the initial forgetting exponent (y_0)—that is, the value prior to any study—can be inferred.

These estimates show that y_0 depends systematically on the position of the item within the list. An empirical function that provides a good fit to these values is:

$$y_0 = \left[\left(\frac{4.2L^{0.82}}{I} \right) + \left(\frac{0.011L^{2.55}}{R} \right) \right]^{(-1)}$$

where L is the length of the list, I is the serial position of the item from the beginning of the list (excluding any prompt), and R is its position counted from the end of the list.

The corresponding initial value of the reducing exponent (q_0), which determines the extent to which the forgetting exponent is reduced during the first study period, was also estimated from the same data. A simple function that provides a good fit is:

$$q_0 = \frac{(I^{-0.5} + R^{-0.5})}{2}$$

When only a single item is considered ($L = 1$, $I = 1$, $R = 1$), these expressions give $y_0 = \frac{1}{4.211}$ and $q_0 = 1$.

These expressions capture the inverted U-shaped variation in the forgetting exponent and the complementary U-shaped variation in the reducing exponent across serial positions.

The model as specified thus far defines the probability of recall of an item following a single study period and the subsequent delay. During study, recall probability increases as an exponential function governed by the parameter k . During the delay, recall declines exponentially at a rate determined by the operative forgetting exponent y_1 , which is derived from its initial value y_0 and reduced during study according to the parameter q_0 . The initial values y_0 and q_0 depend on the position of the item within the list. At short delays, the effective rate of forgetting is modulated by the postponement function α .

This formulation is sufficient to account for recall following a single study period. Its adequacy can be assessed by comparing its predictions with empirical data from studies in which recall is tested after a single exposure.

6. Application of the model to published data

6.1 *Single item, single trial experiments*

Using the parameter values specified above, the model provides an accurate account of the results of Hellyer's (1962) experiment. As shown in Figure 10, it reproduces both the overall form of the forgetting curves and their systematic variation with study duration (1, 2, 4, and 8 seconds), yielding a close correspondence between predicted and observed recall probabilities ($R^2 = 0.9872$).

Hellyer's experiment can be viewed as an extension of the earlier and widely cited study by Peterson and Peterson (1959), in which a consonant trigram was presented auditorily and participants engaged in backward counting during the retention interval.

Peterson and Peterson also recorded the latency of recall—that is, the interval between the recall cue and the response—and their data indicate that successful recall approaches an asymptotic level when this latency reaches approximately 10 seconds. Using this criterion, it is possible to estimate recall probabilities corresponding to responses occurring within this interval.

Figure 10. Model predictions (dashed lines) and observed recall (points) for the short-term forgetting data reported by Hellyer (1962). Increasing study duration leads to a slower rate of decline, and the model captures both the form of the forgetting curves and their systematic dependence on study duration. Right-hand panel: relationship between predicted and observed recall probabilities ($R^2 = 0.987$).

The current model provides an accurate account of these data ($R^2 = 0.9869$), as shown in Figure 10. Importantly, the same parameter values (k , y_0 , q_0 , and α) were used as in the modelling of Hellyer's data, with an assumed effective study duration of 0.5 seconds based on the temporal sequence reported by Peterson and Peterson (1959). The model slightly overestimates recall at longer delays; however, a second experiment reported by Peterson and Peterson, including a comparable 'silent, zero repetition' condition (shown as open circles in Figure 11), aligns more closely with the model predictions.

Figure 11. Left-hand panel: recall probabilities (within 10 seconds) from Peterson and Peterson (1959). Filled circles show results from the first experiment; open circles show a comparable 'silent, zero repetition' condition from a second experiment. The dashed line shows model predictions using the same parameter values as in Figure 10. Right-hand panel: relationship between predicted and observed recall probabilities for the first experiment.

These results show that the core formulation of the model is sufficient to account for short-term forgetting following a single study period across different experimental paradigms. Notably, this fit is achieved without adjusting parameter values across datasets.

6.2 Learning of lists of items

When recall is required only once, as in the experiments of Hellyer (1962) and Peterson and Peterson (1959), the probability of recall following a delay is determined entirely by the operative forgetting exponent γ_1 . However, when items are studied repeatedly across successive trials, the situation is fundamentally different.

In this case, the probability of recall at the end of one trial becomes the starting point for the next. Thus, recall on the second trial begins at p_2 rather than p_0 , and on subsequent trials at p_4 , p_6 , and so on. During each study period, recall probability again increases toward an upper limit, and during each delay it declines. This process is illustrated schematically in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Schematic illustration of the evolution of recall probability across successive study (S_1, S_2, S_3) and delay (D_1, D_2, D_3) periods. The probability of recall at the end of each delay becomes the starting point for the next study period, leading to a progressive increase in recall across trials.

Crucially, accurate prediction of performance across trials requires systematic changes in the operative forgetting exponent governing successive delays. If γ were to remain constant at its initial operative value γ_1 , only a small increase in recall would occur across successive trials, which is insufficient to account for the empirical data. This demonstrates that learning cannot be explained solely by the accumulation of recall probability, but requires systematic changes in the rate of forgetting.

The observed progressive improvement in recall is instead accounted for by a gradual reduction in the forgetting exponent across trials. This reduction is governed by the parameter q , which determines the extent to which γ decreases during each study period. The resulting evolution of γ across successive trials is illustrated in Figure 13.

It would be unrealistic to assume that the forgetting exponent γ simply decreases from trial to trial without any opposing process. While γ is reduced during study periods, there must also be processes that act to restore it toward its initial value γ_0 . These restorative processes do not affect the course of forgetting within a given delay—during which the operative value of γ remains constant—but instead determine the value of γ that applies at the onset of subsequent study periods.

Figure 13. Schematic illustration of the evolution of the forgetting exponent y across successive study (S_1, S_2, S_3) and delay (D_1, D_2, D_3) periods. The continuous curve represents the underlying state variable $y(t)$, which decreases during study and recovers during delay. The dashed horizontal segments represent the operative forgetting exponent governing the probability of recall during each delay period. Each operative value is determined at the end of the preceding study period and remains fixed throughout the subsequent delay.

These processes are represented in the model by the parameter x , which governs the extent to which y returns toward its initial value between successive trials. The role of x becomes important only when learning extends over multiple study–delay cycles: it does not affect recall following a single delay, and is therefore not required to account for short-term forgetting in isolation. When delays between study periods are short, as in continuous list learning, restoration is limited; over longer intervals, it becomes increasingly influential.

The initial value of x , denoted x_0 , depends on list structure and is given by:

$$x_0 = \left[\left(\frac{7.55L}{I^{0.5}} \right) + \left(\frac{14L}{R^{0.5}} \right) \right]^{(-1)}$$

where L is the length of the list, I is the serial position of the item from the beginning of the list (excluding any prompt), and R is its position counted from the end of the list.

The parameter x follows the same general structural pattern as the forgetting exponent y , decreasing during study and potentially recovering during delay. However, in most of the experiments modelled here the restorative exponent z was either zero or extremely small, so changes in x during delay contributed little to the observed behaviour of the model.

The reduction of the forgetting exponent y during study is governed by the parameter q , which determines the extent to which y decreases within each study period (see Figure 13). The value of q increases during study as an exponential function of the square root of time, governed by the exponent w , and may decrease during delay as an exponential function of time governed by the exponent u .

Figure 14. Evolution of the exponent q , which determines the extent to which the forgetting exponent y is reduced during study, across successive study and delay periods. The value of q increases during study and decreases during delay as an exponential function of time.

The value of the forgetting exponent that governs each delay is determined at the onset of that delay, based on the cumulative effects of prior study and delay. This results in a discrete updating of parameter values across trials, rather than a continuous change within a delay period. Such updating should not be interpreted as a discontinuous process in the underlying system, but as a formal representation of how prior history shapes subsequent forgetting. The parameter x decreases exponentially as a function of the square root of study time, with an exponent v , and potentially an exponential increase in x during the delay period with an exponent z . In experiments involving the cyclic learning of lists with only the rest of the list to cause a delay between readings z was 0 (i.e., no increase in x occurred during the delay periods).

In the various experiments to which the model was applied v did not vary from item to item, or across trials, but it did depend on the length of the list and it varied from one experiment to another. The best estimate of v that could be calculated from Robinson and Brown's data was as follows:

$$v = 0.057L^{0.2}$$

where L is the length of the list

The reduction of the forgetting exponent y during study is governed by a further parameter, q , which determines the extent to which y decreases within each study period (see Figure 14). The

exponent q increases exponentially with the square root of study time, governed by the exponent w , and decreases during delay periods as an exponential function of time governed by the exponent u .

In modelling the learning of lists by Ebbinghaus and by Robinson and Brown, $u = 0$, indicating that no decrease in q occurred during delay periods. In experiments involving delays of only a few minutes, w did not vary across trials; however, it is designated here as w_0 to allow for the possibility that it may vary under other conditions.

The parameters y and x differ from q (and, later, w) in that they directly determine the form of forgetting within a given delay period. For this reason, their operative values must remain constant throughout that delay. By contrast, q does not directly influence the course of forgetting within the delay, but instead determines how the forgetting exponent is modified during study. It can therefore be modelled as varying continuously during delay periods without affecting the form of the current forgetting function.

The best estimate of w_0 that could be calculated from Robinson and Brown's data was as follows:

$$w_0 = \left(\frac{0.7}{LI^{0.5}} + \frac{0.2}{LR^{0.5}} \right)$$

where L is the length of the list, I is the serial position of the item from the beginning of the list (excluding any prompt), and R is its position counted from the end of the list.

When recall follows a single presentation and delay, the forgetting rate is determined entirely by y and q , as these alone govern the decline from p_1 to p_2 . In contrast, when lists of items are learned through successive readings without delay between presentations, additional parameters — x , w , and v — are required. Following a summary of the various model parameters the model specified above, incorporating these interacting parameters, will be applied to the data of Robinson and Brown (1926) and to the principal findings of Ebbinghaus (1885/1964).

6.3 Model parameters and their functional roles

At this stage it is useful to summarise the various model parameters and their roles. The model is expressed in terms of a set of interacting parameters that determine how recall probability evolves across successive periods of study and delay. For clarity, each parameter is described below in terms of both its symbol and its functional role within the model. Some of the higher-level parameters described below (particularly f and g) are introduced formally only in later sections dealing with learning and forgetting over extended intervals, but are included here for completeness.

Core process

p — *probability of recall*: the likelihood that an item can be correctly recalled at a given point in time.

Forgetting dynamics

y — *forgetting exponent*: an underlying state variable governing the rate at which recall probability declines during delay periods. During study, y decreases; during delay it tends to recover toward its initial level. The probability of recall within a given delay is determined by the operative forgetting exponent established at the end of the preceding study period, which remains fixed throughout that delay. Higher operative values of y correspond to more rapid forgetting.

Modification of forgetting during study

q — *reducing exponent*: governs the extent to which the forgetting exponent y is reduced during a study period. Higher values of q produce a greater reduction in y , leading to slower subsequent forgetting.

Higher-level modulation of learning

w — *modulating exponent*: determines how the reducing exponent q changes across successive study and delay periods, and thus how the effects of learning accumulate over time.

Dynamics of the modulating exponent

f — *growth exponent of w* : governs the increase of w during study periods in experiments involving repeated learning over extended intervals.

g — *decay exponent of w* : governs the decrease of w during delay periods as a function of relative time in experiments involving extended retention intervals.

Restoration processes during delay

x — *restorative exponent*: governs the tendency of the underlying forgetting state variable y to recover toward its initial value during delay periods.

z — *exponent governing changes in x* : determines the extent to which the restorative exponent x varies across study and delay periods.

Additional modulation of learning dynamics

u — *decay exponent of q* : governs the decrease of the reducing exponent q during delay periods.

Study dynamics

k — *acquisition exponent*: governs the rate at which recall probability increases during study.

Initial values

y_0 — initial forgetting exponent (before study)

q_0 — initial reducing exponent

x_0 — initial restorative exponent

w_0 — initial modulating exponent governing q

Temporal scaling

Relative time (D_r) — the ratio of total elapsed time from the start of initial learning to the end of a delay, to the elapsed time from the start of learning to the end of the most recent study period. This measure is used to model processes operating over extended intervals.

Taken together, these parameters define a system of interacting processes in which changes in recall probability arise from the evolving values of the forgetting exponent, and in which the evolution of each parameter depends on the state of others over successive study and delay periods.

6.4 Data of Robinson and Brown (1926)

The model provides a close quantitative account of the learning of lists of nonsense syllables in Robinson and Brown's (1926) study. This fit arises from the interaction of the parameters governing the reduction of the forgetting exponent during study and its evolution across successive trials. Figure 15 shows the model's predictions for the progressive learning of items in the shortest (5 items) and longest (17 items) lists employed in the study. For the remaining list lengths (8, 11,

and 14 items), the correspondence between predicted and observed recall probabilities is similarly strong, with linear fits yielding R^2 values exceeding 0.98.

Figure 16 illustrates the model's ability to capture the learning trajectories of individual items. The figure shows predictions for four items in the 17-syllable list for which Robinson and Brown provided the most complete data. Despite substantial variation in learning rates across items, the model closely reproduces the observed recall probabilities across trials. Comparable fits were obtained for the remaining items in this list (see Appendix 2) and for items in lists of other lengths.

Figure 15. Upper panels: Model predictions (broken lines) and observed recall (points) for successive trials in the shortest (5 items; trials 1–5) and longest (17 items; trials 1, 5, 9, 13, and 17) lists reported by Robinson and Brown (1926). Each curve corresponds to a different trial, with later trials showing progressively higher recall and a less pronounced serial position effect. Lower panels: The linear relationship between predicted and observed recall probabilities for the two list lengths.

Figure 16. Model predictions (dashed lines) and observed recall (points) for the progressive learning of the four items in Robinson and Brown’s 17-syllable list for which they provided the most complete data. The figure illustrates the close correspondence between predicted and observed recall across all serial positions, despite substantial variation in learning rates between items. Similar fits were obtained for the other items in the 17-syllable list (see Appendix 2) and all the individual items in the list of other lengths

Across the five list lengths reported by Robinson and Brown (1926), a total of 460 data points were available, representing the probability of recall of individual items at different stages of learning. Figure 17 shows the relationship between predicted and observed values across this entire dataset, demonstrating a high level of overall agreement ($R^2 = 0.9679$).

Figure 17. Relationship between predicted and observed probabilities of recall across all items, trials, and list lengths in Robinson and Brown’s (1926) data ($N = 460$).

In generating these predictions, the parameters k , y_0 , q_0 , x_0 , and w_0 were set as specified previously. The postponement factor α was omitted (i.e., set effectively to 1), as the shortest delay before recall (10 seconds) substantially exceeds the interval over which postponement operates.

Taken together, these results show that the model captures both the detailed learning trajectories of individual items and the overall structure of recall across lists and trials.

7. Modelling Ebbinghaus' results

The model's ability to reproduce the data of Robinson and Brown reflects the fact that it was developed with reference to those data. A more stringent test is therefore provided by its ability to account for independent findings, such as those reported by Ebbinghaus.

7.1 Criterion of learning

Ebbinghaus did not report how individual items in his lists were acquired; instead, he recorded only the number of 'readings' (or, in some cases, the time) required to learn each list as a whole. As noted earlier, a list can be considered to be fully learned only when the slowest item has reached a level at which it can be correctly recalled.

To apply the model to these data, trial-by-trial predictions were generated for each item in a list, as in the case of Robinson and Brown. However, because Ebbinghaus reported only the point at which a list was learned to criterion, it was necessary to define a probability threshold corresponding to successful recall for each individual item. This threshold cannot be 1.00, as the exponential formulation of the model approaches but never reaches unity.

An empirical estimate of this threshold was obtained from the data of Robinson and Brown. For each item, the predicted probability of recall was identified for the first trial on which that item was recalled correctly. An example is shown in Figure 18. Across all items and trials, the mean predicted probability at this point was 0.9825. This value was therefore adopted as the operational criterion for successful recall in modelling Ebbinghaus' data.

Figure 18. Example of the predicted probability associated with the first trial on which an item was recalled correctly in Robinson and Brown's (1926) data.

A list was considered to be learned when the slowest item reached this criterion. The model therefore yields predictions in terms of the whole number of readings required to learn each list. Where Ebbinghaus reported his results in the same units, comparison between predicted and

observed values is direct. In many cases, however, Ebbinghaus reported learning time rather than number of readings. To enable comparison, a conversion between time and readings was required.

Ebbinghaus reported the average time required per syllable for lists of different lengths (Table 1). By multiplying this value by the number of syllables in a list, the duration of a single reading can be estimated. This allows reported times to be converted into equivalent numbers of readings, and predicted readings to be expressed in time units.

Length of list	Average time required (sec.)
12	0.416
16	0.427
24	0.438
36	0.459

Table 1. Average time per syllable for lists of different lengths (Ebbinghaus, 1964, p. 33).

7.2 Learning lists of different lengths

To predict the number of readings required for Ebbinghaus to learn lists of different lengths, the parameters k , y_0 , q_0 , x_0 , and w_0 were set as specified earlier. However, a different value of v was required to account for the effect of list length in this context:

$$v = 0.08L^{0.2}$$

For the postponement factor α , the optimal values of b and D_τ were found to be 3 and 4.52, respectively.

Figure 19. Left-hand panel: Model predictions (dashed line and open symbols) and observed data (filled symbols) for the number of readings required to learn lists of different lengths, based on Ebbinghaus (1885/1964). Right-hand panel: Relationship between predicted and observed number of readings across conditions.

As shown in Figure 19, the model reproduces with near-perfect accuracy ($R^2 = 0.9997$) the relationship reported by Ebbinghaus between list length and the number of readings required for learning (see Figure 1).

This result is notable because the model was not fitted to these data, but generates the observed relationship from parameters constrained by other experimental findings.

7.3 Ebbinghaus' experiments involving delays before relearning of 24 hours

A number of Ebbinghaus' experiments involved repeated learning with delays of 24 hours between successive sessions. Extending the model to account for these longer intervals requires the introduction of additional components—specifically the parameters f and g , which modify the evolution of w —while retaining the structure described above. These components are introduced in relation to the specific experimental findings they are required to explain.

7.3.1 Repeated relearning

This experiment examined whether relearning becomes progressively easier across repeated exposures. Ebbinghaus learned lists of nonsense syllables of different lengths (12, 24, and 36 items), relearned them after a delay of 24 hours, and repeated this procedure on four further occasions at the same interval.

He reported the number of readings required to learn or relearn each list on each of six successive days. These data are shown in Figure 20, both in tabular form and graphically.

Ebbinghaus observed that although the number of readings initially required varied substantially with list length, the number required for relearning became progressively more similar across conditions. However, he was unable to identify a simple quantitative relationship underlying this pattern, noting that “a simple conformity to law cannot be discovered in this successively decreasing necessity for work” (Ebbinghaus, 1964, p. 85).

This convergence across list lengths provides a stringent test for the model, as it requires the interaction of learning and forgetting processes over extended intervals to produce a systematic reduction in differences between conditions.

Figure 20. Number of readings required to learn or relearn lists of 12, 24, and 36 items across six successive days (Ebbinghaus, 1885/1964). Left: tabulated values. Right: the same data shown graphically.

The data exhibit some irregularities. For example, on Day 1 the list of 36 syllables required 55 readings, whereas the list of 24 required 44; by Day 3, the corresponding values were 11 and 12.5, respectively. It is unlikely that the longer list genuinely became easier to learn than the shorter one; such reversals are more plausibly attributable to measurement variability in the data.

In addition, the model generates predictions in terms of whole numbers of readings, whereas Ebbinghaus' reported values include fractional readings derived from averaging across trials. These factors limit the extent to which exact correspondence can be expected.

Nevertheless, as shown in Figure 21, the model provides a close account of the data ($R^2 = 0.9741$). Importantly, it captures the overall convergence of learning across list lengths despite these irregularities.

Figure 21. Left-hand panels: number of readings required to learn lists of 12, 24, and 36 syllables across six successive days, as reported by Ebbinghaus (filled symbols), together with model predictions (dashed lines). Right-hand panel: relationship between predicted and observed number of readings across all conditions (3 list lengths \times 6 days).

The progressive reduction in the number of readings required across successive relearning sessions cannot be accounted for by the previously defined parameters alone, as they do not produce sufficient acceleration of learning across trials. To reproduce these data, an additional exponent f was introduced, which governs the increase of w across successive study periods. In the present experiment, $f = 0.0405$. This parameter allows the rate at which learning accumulates to increase across successive study periods.

Parameters governing changes during delay (g , z , and u) were set to zero, indicating that w , x , and q remained unchanged during the 24-hour intervals between study sessions.

7.3.2 *The amount of initial learning ('prelearning') on relearning*

Ebbinghaus investigated how the amount retained after a delay depends on the degree of initial learning. Although prior study reduces the effort required for relearning, an important question is whether this benefit exhibits diminishing returns as the amount of initial learning increases.

To examine this, Ebbinghaus studied groups of six lists of nonsense syllables, each containing 16 items. He had previously established that learning such a group from scratch required approximately 1,270 seconds, corresponding to about 31–33 readings (based on an average rate of 0.427 seconds per syllable). In modelling these data, a value of 33 readings was used.

In the experiment, the lists were read a specified number of times on Day 1 (8, 16, 24, 32, 42, 53, or 64 readings), and were then relearned to criterion after a delay of 24 hours. The time required for relearning on Day 2 was recorded. By comparing this with the baseline time required to learn

a new set of lists (1,270 seconds), Ebbinghaus derived a measure of time saved due to prior learning.

The relationship between initial study and subsequent savings is shown in Figure 22. The data reveal a highly systematic relationship between the number of initial readings and the benefit observed during relearning 24 hours later, both in terms of total relearning time and percentage savings.

Figure 22. Time saved during relearning (Day 2) as a function of the number of initial readings on Day 1 for six lists of 16 nonsense syllables (Ebbinghaus, 1885/1964).

As shown in Figure 23, the model closely reproduces these results. In particular, it provides an accurate account of the percentage of time saved during relearning ($R^2 = 0.9896$).

In these simulations, the parameter ν was set as in the previous Ebbinghaus analyses. The exponent f was 0.02 and z was 0.00004, while g and u were set to zero.

This result is notable because it captures the diminishing returns of additional study within a unified framework, without requiring a separate mechanism to account for savings.

Figure 23. Left-hand panel: Relationship between predicted and observed number of relearning trials. Right-hand panel: Relationship between predicted and observed percentage savings across conditions.

7.3.3 ‘Massive overlearning’ experiment

In a further study, Ebbinghaus examined the effects of what may be termed ‘massive overlearning’. A list of 12 nonsense syllables was read a total of four times longer than was required to achieve an accurate recitation during initial learning. This corresponded to 68 readings in total, given that initial learning required 17 readings (excluding the first correct recitation). The list was then relearned to the same criterion after a delay of 24 hours.

Figure 24. Model prediction of learning and relearning in Ebbinghaus’ “massive overlearning” experiment. Open circles indicate the readings at which the list was first mastered (Day 1) and subsequently relearned (Day 2); filled symbols show the corresponding model predictions.

Although this experiment does not introduce a qualitatively new pattern, it provides a stringent test of the model under conditions of extended study. As shown in Figure 24, the model accurately predicts both the point of initial mastery and the point of successful relearning after the delay.

In this case, the parameters f , g , and z were set to zero, while $u = 0.33$ and $v = 0.192$.

8. Studies that involved delays of more than 24 hours.

The final experiment of Ebbinghaus considered here is his well-known study of forgetting (see Figure 3), which includes a condition involving a delay of up to 30 days before relearning. In addition, the study by Perkins (1914), discussed below, also involves an extended delay (14 days) before recall. These experiments provide a test of the model under conditions in which learning and forgetting unfold over substantially longer timescales.

It is well established that forgetting over extended intervals is often well described by power functions of time (e.g., Anderson, 1995; Wixted & Ebbesen, 1991). However, such functions have an undesirable property when applied directly: they approach infinity as time approaches zero, implying unrealistically high values at the point of immediate recall.

One way to address this issue is to recognise that, in many learning situations, the effective passage of time is not well captured by absolute units such as seconds or minutes. Instead, what is often critical is the relationship between the time of recall and the total duration over which learning has taken place. This suggests the use of a *relative* measure of time, in which the relevant interval is scaled by the total time from the beginning of the first study period to the end of the most recent one. When time is expressed in these units, the point of immediate recall corresponds to a value of 1 rather than 0, and functions that would otherwise be problematic at zero can be applied without difficulty.

The present model is formulated primarily in terms of exponential functions and this relative measure of time proves necessary in one specific context. In particular, it is required to describe the processes that operate over extended periods of study and long intervals between study and relearning. These processes depend not simply on the absolute duration of the delay, but on its duration relative to the total prior history of learning.

Figure 25. Evolution of the exponent w , which governs the increase of qv during study, across successive study and delay periods. During study periods, w increases as a function of \sqrt{S} (with exponent f); during delays, it may decrease as a function of relative time D_r (with exponent g). Relative time (D_r) is the ratio of total elapsed time (from the start of initial learning to the end of the current delay) to the elapsed time from the start of initial learning up to the end of the most recent study period, thereby scaling delay as a proportion of prior learning history.

Within the model, this effect is captured by the exponent g , which governs the reduction of the exponent w during delay periods. The parameter w determines how the exponent q varies across study and delay intervals (see Figure 14). During study, w increases as a function of the square root of time, governed by the exponent f . During delays, however, w decreases as a function of relative time, with the rate of this decrease determined by g (see Figure 25).

The use of relative time in this context allows the model to capture the effects of extended spacing and long delays, while maintaining a consistent exponential framework.

8.1 Ebbinghaus' 'forgetting' experiment

Ebbinghaus reported the results of his forgetting experiment (see Figure 3) in terms of time and the percentage of time saved during relearning. When these times are converted into whole numbers of readings, the model reproduces the form of the forgetting curve with very high accuracy ($R^2 \approx 1.00$), as shown in Figure 26.

To account for forgetting over such extended intervals, the model employs the exponent g , which governs the reduction of w during delay periods as a function of relative time (defined in the preceding section). This allows the effects of delay to be scaled relative to the prior history of learning and enables the model to capture both the rapid initial decline and the slower long-term rate of forgetting observed in Ebbinghaus' data.

In generating these predictions, the parameter values were $f = 0.128$, $g = 0.00004$, $u = 0.4$, $v = 0.192$, and $z = 0.000017$.

Figure 26. Model reproduction of the savings curve reported by Ebbinghaus (1885/1964), showing both the rapid initial decline and the slower rate of forgetting over extended intervals. Empirical data are shown as points and a continuous line; model predictions are shown as open symbols. The agreement between predicted and observed values is high across the full range of retention intervals.

When the model's predictions (expressed in whole numbers of readings) are converted back into time, the correspondence with Ebbinghaus' reported values remains close, although small discrepancies arise due to this conversion (see Figure 27).

Figure 27. Left-hand panel: comparison between Ebbinghaus' forgetting curve (solid symbols and line) and that generated by the current model (open symbols) after converting predicted readings into time. Right-hand panel: relationship between predicted and observed values expressed in time units. Note: Ebbinghaus reported his results in terms of time, whereas the model generates predictions in terms of whole numbers of readings; conversion between these units introduces small discrepancies.

8.2 Massed versus distributed practice; Perkins (1914)

Perkins (1914) was one of the first to investigate massed versus distributed learning in a systematic manner. As described earlier, she employed 16 conditions in which a list of 14 nonsense syllables was studied in blocks of 1, 2, 4, or 8 readings, spaced at intervals of 1, 2, 3, or 4 days, until a total of 16 readings had been completed. Thus, learning could take place over as few as two days (8 readings per session with a 1-day interval) or as many as 61 days (1 reading per session with 4-day intervals). Recall of the list was tested 14 days after the final reading.

An attempt was made to reproduce Perkins' results using the current model. This required some approximation, as participants learned the syllables in pairs separated by brief intervals. Each pair was presented for 3 seconds; this was treated as equivalent to 1.5 seconds per individual item. In addition, the number of participants varied across conditions, introducing some irregularity into the data.

Figure 28. Model predictions for Perkins' (1914) experiment. Top-left panel shows observed recall (symbols) and model predictions (dashed line). Bottom-left panel shows the relationship between predicted and observed values. Right-hand panels compare observed (solid lines) and predicted (dashed lines) recall across block sizes for each spacing interval.

As shown in Figure 28, the model produces predictions that closely resemble the observed data (overall $R^2 = 0.9616$), particularly with respect to the effect of block size. Within the range of intervals employed by Perkins, the model predicts that smaller blocks of study lead to better subsequent recall than larger blocks, whereas variation in the spacing between blocks has a comparatively modest effect once intervals of at least one day are used.

This pattern arises from the way relative time influences the evolution of w during delay periods. Smaller blocks necessarily involve a greater number of study–delay cycles, which reduces the relative duration of each delay when expressed as a proportion of the total learning history. As a result, w declines less during each delay.

Because w governs the rate at which q decreases, this leads to higher values of q , which in turn produce a greater reduction in the forgetting exponent y during subsequent study periods. The net effect is a slower rate of forgetting and improved recall for conditions involving smaller blocks of study. In particular, the advantage of distributed practice arises because shorter relative delays

preserve higher values of w , thereby sustaining the capacity for further reduction in the forgetting exponent across study episodes.

This provides a mechanistic account of the spacing effect in terms of the interaction between study structure and the scaling of delay by prior learning history. Importantly, this effect emerges from the structure of the model rather than from any parameter specific to spacing, indicating that the spacing effect arises naturally from the interaction between study scheduling and the dynamics of forgetting.

In generating these predictions, u and z were set to zero, while $f = 0.199$, $g = 0.02$, and $v = 0.34$.

9. Summary of model structure

The model is expressed in terms of a set of interacting exponents that determine how the probability of recall evolves across study and delay. At this point, it is useful to summarise its structure in terms of the hierarchy of processes involved.

The model comprises four levels of interacting exponents. Each level determines how the processes at the level above it evolve over time, so that behaviour at the level of recall probability emerges from underlying dynamics operating across multiple timescales.

Level 1. The probability of recall (p) increases during study as a function of the acquisition exponent k and decreases during delay as a function of the forgetting exponent y .

Level 2. The forgetting exponent (y) is reduced during study by the reducing exponent q and tends to increase during delay under the influence of the restorative exponent x .

Level 3. The reducing exponent (q) increases during study as a function of w and may decrease during delay under the influence of u . The restorative exponent (x) may decrease during study as a function of v and increase during delay under the influence of z .

Level 4. The parameter w , which governs changes in q , increases during study under the influence of f and decreases during delay as a function of g , which operates over relative time.

Figure 29. Hierarchical structure of the model. The probability of recall (p) is determined by the forgetting exponent (y); changes in y are governed by the reducing exponent (q) and restorative exponent (x); and changes in q are modulated by the higher-level exponent (w).

This hierarchical structure captures the way in which processes operating over shorter timescales are progressively shaped by processes operating over longer timescales. In this way, the

observed behaviour of recall probability reflects the cumulative effects of interacting processes across successive levels of the model.

Figures 13, 14 and 26 illustrate the evolution of these parameters across study and delay periods, a schematic representation of the hierarchical organisation of the model is shown in Figure 29 and Appendix 1 provides the parameter values used in each of the experiments modelled.

10. Conclusion

Relatively few studies have provided the level of quantitative detail required to support analyses of the kind undertaken here. The experiments considered are drawn largely from an earlier period in the development of psychology, when such detail was more commonly reported. Although previous work has modelled individual findings—for example, the forgetting curve described by Ebbinghaus—no single model has been proposed that accounts for such a range of results within a unified quantitative framework. The model presented here demonstrates that this is possible and provides a basis for a more integrated understanding of fundamental memory processes.

A central implication of the model is that, for individual items and lists of unrelated items, forgetting proceeds in a smooth and continuous manner following a brief initial period during which little or no measurable forgetting occurs. Beyond this short interval, there is no clear need to posit two qualitatively distinct processes corresponding to ‘short-term’ and ‘long-term’ memory. In particular, the findings analysed here do not require the interpretation proposed by Atkinson and Shiffrin (1968), in which rapid decay over approximately 15 seconds reflects the operation of a short-term store and residual performance reflects transfer to a long-term store. Instead, these results can be understood in terms of a single, continuously evolving process.

Findings such as those of Ebbinghaus (1885/1964), Peterson and Peterson (1959), and Perkins (1914) are frequently cited as demonstrations of basic memory phenomena, but are often presented without a detailed account of the quantitative principles that govern them or of the relationships between them. The model developed here provides such an account, situating these phenomena within a coherent and unified framework.

The present analyses have been conducted under conditions in which recall can be expressed in terms of the probability of retrieving discrete items of known informational content. Such conditions are most readily achieved in controlled experimental settings using relatively simple materials. In many real-world contexts, however, what is retained and recalled is structured and meaningful material, the effective information content of which depends on its organisation and on the prior knowledge of the individual. Although this makes precise quantification more difficult, it does not imply that different principles are required. Rather, it suggests that the same underlying processes operate on representations whose effective informational structure is more complex.

The challenge for future work is therefore to extend these principles to situations in which the organisation and informational content of material can be more fully characterised. In this way, the model offers a quantitative framework within which both controlled experimental findings and more complex forms of memory can be understood as expressions of the same underlying processes.

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Appendices

	k	b	D_τ	y_0	q_0	x_0	w_0	f	g	u	v	z
Peterson & Peterson	√	2.25	3.2	√	√							
Hellyer	√	2.25	3.2	√	√							
Robinson & Brown	√			√	√	√	√	0	0	0	$0.057*(L^{0.2})$	0
Ebbinghaus learning lists	√	3	4.52	√	√	√	√	0	0	0	$0.08*(L^{0.2})$	0
Ebbinghaus relearning lists	√			√	√	√	√	0.0405	0	0	$0.08*(L^{0.2})$	0
Ebbinghaus prelearning lists	√			√	√	√	√	0.02	0	0	$0.08*(L^{0.2})$	0.00004
Ebbinghaus overlearning list	√			√	√	√	√	0	0	0.33	0.192	0
Ebbinghaus forgetting expt	√			√	√	√	√	0.128	0.00004	0.4	0.192	0.000017
Perkins	√			√	√	√	√	0.271	0.12	0	0.36	0
√ indicates that the parameter was included and calculated as specified in the model												
$k = 360I^{-2}$ $y_0 = \left[\left(\frac{4.2L^{0.82}}{I} \right) + \left(\frac{0.011L^{2.55}}{R} \right) \right]^{(-1)}$ $q_0 = \frac{(I^{-0.5} + R^{-0.5})}{2}$ $\alpha = (1 + e^{-b(D - D_\tau)})^{-1}$ $x_0 = \left[\left(\frac{7.55L}{I^{0.5}} \right) + \left(\frac{14L}{R^{0.5}} \right) \right]^{(-1)}$ $w_0 = \left(\frac{0.7}{LI^{0.5}} + \frac{0.2}{LR^{0.5}} \right)$ <p>L = the length of the list I = the item's number counting from the beginning of the list (excluding the prompt) R = the item's number counting from the end of the list,</p>												

Appendix 1. The values of the exponents employed in reproducing the results of the various experiments dealt with here.

Appendix 2. The predictions of the model (shown as dashed lines) for the progressive learning of each of the nonsense syllables in Robinson & Brown's (1926) list of 17 syllables. The actual data are shown as diamonds. The vertical axes represent the probability of recall and the horizontal axes the trials.